

Using AI-Powered Tools to Develop Critical Thinking Skills among Students in EFL Writing: Perceptions and Challenges

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Abstract

This study explores perceptions and challenges associated with using AI-powered tools to enhance EFL students' critical thinking skills in writing. To collect data, we employed a mixed-methods approach involving questionnaires administered to 30 EFL students and interviews with six EFL teachers from the Department of Foreign Languages at the University of Djelfa, Algeria. As a result, the findings of the present study suggest that participants view AI-powered tools as beneficial for enhancing critical thinking skills in EFL writing. Nonetheless, challenges such as overreliance on AI and a lack of personalisation in AI-based tools could hinder students' progress. Further studies may be needed to explore new ways to adapt to and leverage the emergence of AI in education while overcoming potential challenges.

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1. Introduction

In the digital era, technological developments are advancing at a rapid pace. One notable example of these innovative advancements is the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI impacts various aspects of our everyday lives, including education. There is a growing interest among scholars to provide evidence supporting the effectiveness of personalised teaching systems, which are widely adopted to improve learning outcomes (Khosravi et al., 2022). For instance, Automated Writing Evaluation (AWE) systems, Automated Essay Evaluation (AEE) systems, and chatbots exemplify the use of AI-powered tools in EFL instruction, specifically for enhancing EFL students' writing skills.

However, most existing studies tend to investigate the effectiveness of these tools in improving learners' writing competency at the word and sentence levels. Indeed, there is limited research exploring the impact of AI-powered tools on EFL students' writing skills at a higher level, focusing on aspects such as idea generation, content, coherence, organization, argumentation, and other elements that require critical thinking (CT) abilities. In an era of rapidly increasing technological advancements and a constant flow of information, the acquisition of CT is becoming a crucial objective for educational systems (Alharbi, 2022).

This study aims to explore the impact of using AI tools to develop students' CT, building upon Bloom's taxonomy in EFL

writing. Therefore, it addresses the two following main questions:

- What are teachers' and students' perceptions of the use of AI-powered to enhance CT skills in EFL writing?
- What potential challenges do EFL students encounter in this context?

The research is conducted at the University of Djelfa, Algeria, within the Department of Foreign Languages. We believe this study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge aimed at enhancing personalised learning in an AI-based educational setting.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Defining Key Terms

Before elaborating on the actual literature review, it would be beneficial to clarify the key terms of this research study.

2.1.1 Writing Skills

Writing skills are a significant aspect of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learning. Indeed, according to Harmer, writing is a key component of language learning (Harmer, 1998 as cited in Faraj, 2015). Writing might seem as simple as putting words on a paper in a certain order. Nevertheless, writing is a complex process that involves other aspects in terms of thinking, composing and encoding language into a written text that fits within a particular socio-cultural context (Cumming, 1998). Indeed, writing is a way

of representing ideas, experiences and stories so that the writer conveys the meanings of their thoughts to others (Groenewold & Hayden, 1989).

2.1.2 Artificial Intelligence

John McCarthy first coined the term "Artificial Intelligence" at a Dartmouth conference in 1956 (Kota, 2018). Since then, several definitions have been proposed. One defines AI as "the study of mental faculties through the use of computational models" (Charniak, 1985). Marvin Minsky defines AI as "... the science of making machines do things that would require intelligence if done by men" (Bolter, 1986, p. 193 as cited in Fjelland, 2020). AI is a field of computer science focused on developing machines capable of emulating human-like intelligent behavior (Russell et al., 2010). AI draws on knowledge and techniques from various disciplines—including computer science, logic, biology, psychology, and philosophy—and has contributed to significant advancements in applications such as speech recognition, image processing, natural language processing, automated theorem proving, and intelligent robotics (Zhang & Lu, 2021). In today's digital era, AI plays a vital role in social development (Zhang & Lu, 2021). AI continues to advance and is expected to help individuals and societies perform complex tasks more efficiently and accurately (Morandín-Ahuerma, 2022).

2.1.3 Critical Thinking

Despite the significant importance of CT, there is less consensus on its definition.

Scholars have described it through various concepts such as a trait, attitude, ability, or a combination of specific skills (Lamont, 2020). Some argue that CT closely resembles informal logic (Ennis, 1984; Possin, 2008; Sobocan, 2003, as cited in Lamont, 2020). Indeed, it includes specific skills such as the evaluation of reasons and the identification of fallacies (Ennis, 1996, as cited in Aghajani & Gholamrezapour, 2019). Others refer to it as scientific thinking promoting impartiality and rationality (Halpern, 1984; Sternberg et al., 2007, as cited in Lamont, 2020). CT are advanced cognitive abilities that involve the purposeful and self-regulated analysis and evaluation of arguments, requiring skills such as interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference of information (Astleitner, 2007, as cited in Aghajani & Gholamrezapour, 2019). In summary, definitions of CT can be classified into three main perspectives: 1) a focus on mental processes, 2) a focus on CT skills, and 3) a focus on the outcomes of CT (Al-Ghadouni, 2021).

2.2 Related Works

2.2.1 Autonomous Writing in EFL

In a recent study, Truong and Nguyen (2023) conducted a qualitative research study to explore EFL teachers' perceptions of the need to promote students' writing autonomy at a public high school in Vietnam. The findings showed that all teachers believe developing writing autonomy among EFL students is essential. Blogging is one approach that may foster students' independent writing skills. According to Soner's 2020 study on the

impact of blogging in academic writing, results showed an increase in success scores among EFL students who used blogging to develop their writing skills. The same study also indicated that students exhibited a positive attitude towards using blogs in their writing practice (Sütçü, 2020).

In another study, (Razali, 2013) used a qualitative methodology to examine six students, collecting data through observation and interviews over thirty days to investigate the impact of Facebook groups on promoting independent writing skills. Findings demonstrated a positive impact of this tool on students' writing abilities. Moreover, Sheerah and Yadav's study explored the effectiveness of writing hub learning strategies in developing EFL students' autonomous writing skills. Results showed that these strategies were successful in enhancing writing autonomy among learners. Nevertheless, the authors suggest that the concept of learning autonomy and learners' involvement in it should be clarified before implementation (Sheerah & Yadav, 2022).

2.2.2 AI-assisted Writing in EFL

Technology is becoming an integral part of our everyday lives and continues to advance rapidly. AI is one of the most rapidly growing areas in technology, becoming a major trend. Consequently, it has contributed to societal development in numerous aspects. For instance, the field of education is leveraging the emergence of AI-powered technologies. AI in Education (AIED) was projected to grow by 43% from 2018 to 2022 (Becker et al., 2018, as cited

in Jiang, 2022). Writing is a challenging skill for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction. Consequently, several studies have explored the potential of incorporating AI in EFL contexts to reduce writing challenges and improve efficiency.

A) The Use of AI-Powered Tools Impact on Learners' Writing Performance

Using AWE systems powered by AI has a positive impact on learners' writing performance, and they are increasingly adopted in EFL classes across various educational institutions. A recent study (Geng & Razali, 2022) investigated the effectiveness of automated feedback from AWE programs in developing undergraduate students' writing skills by reviewing eleven articles published in the past five years, synthesising findings through a literature review matrix. The study findings identify four potential benefits of AWE programs: improving students' overall writing performance, enhancing analytical writing skills, fostering revision abilities, and increasing writing knowledge (Geng & Razali, 2022).

"Write and Improve," an online AWE tool developed by the University of Cambridge, has demonstrated theoretical and practical value in language learning for higher education, as noted by Karpova (2020). In his research, he aimed to illustrate that "Write and Improve" is an example of innovative technology that help students improve writing as a critical academic skill. In fact, the findings confirmed the effectiveness of "Write and Improve" in enhancing students' writing skills in higher education.

At the college level, Lu (2019) conducted an empirical study in China, using an experimental approach to explore the effectiveness of Juku—one of the most commonly used AWE systems in Chinese colleges and universities—in enhancing students' writing skills. Results indicated that AWE is an effective tool for enhancing students' writing skills.

In a separate study, Abdalkader (2022) posed the research question, “How can a program based on AI applications in education be designed to enhance EFL students' writing fluency?” This study aimed to investigate the effect of AI-based activities on enhancing writing fluency among preparatory-level students in Distinguished Governmental Language Schools. A quasi-experimental approach was used with a group of students to achieve the study's goals. The results indicated a positive effect of AI applications on enhancing writing fluency among third preparatory stage students.

Other studies have examined the effectiveness of AI-powered writing assistants in fostering EFL students' writing skills. For instance, two studies investigated the impact of Grammarly on EFL students' writing skills, employing both qualitative and quantitative methods. Findings from both studies highlighted Grammarly's positive impact on students' writing abilities (Labidi, 2022; Nur Fitria, 2021).

B) Students' Perceptions and Emotions Towards the Use of AI for Writing

Enhancing EFL students' writing performance through AI-powered tools is not the sole focus of educational scholars. Some studies have also explored learning behavior and technology acceptance related to these tools. For instance, Nazari et al. investigated whether an AI-powered writing tool could efficiently promote learning behavior and attitudinal technology acceptance through formative feedback and assessment for non-native postgraduate students in English academic writing. Findings from an experiment with 120 students revealed that those in the AI intervention group showed statistically significant improvements in behavioral engagement, emotional engagement, cognitive engagement, and self-efficacy for writing (Nazari et al., 2021).

Nonetheless, Wang et al. (2022) suggest that combining AI-based Automated Writing Evaluation technology with virtual reality could positively impact EFL writing motivation compared to using the conventional AWE approach alone. Results from a quasi-experiment with two groups of students indicated that the Spherical Video-based Virtual Reality (SVVR)-AWE approach significantly enhanced EFL writing performance, increased motivation, self-efficacy, and sense of presence, while reducing writing anxiety.

Additionally, in a study by Sumakul et al. (2022), data was collected through semi-structured interviews with EFL students in an English Language Education department at an Indonesian university. The study aimed to investigate students' perceptions of AI use in their learning, specifically within a writing class. Results

indicated that students held positive perceptions of AI-powered writing tools.

The literature suggests that researchers generally agree on the effectiveness of AI-powered writing tools in enhancing EFL writing instruction and learning. However, beyond issues of affordability, access, and users' familiarity with this technology, the nature of EFL writing itself warrants further investigation. This will be the focus of the present study.

2.2.3 Literature Gap: CT Skills Development in an AI-assisted EFL Writing Context

Scholars in education contend that CT skills (CT skills) are crucial in today's fast-paced, evolving world (Costa, 2001; Lipman, 2003, as cited in Alharbi, 2022). Therefore, to equip students with the skills needed to tackle future challenges, educators must effectively teach and assess CT, preparing students with competencies relevant to the demands of the twenty-first century (Hove, 2011, as cited in Alharbi, 2022). Teaching EFL writing presents an opportunity to develop students' CT skills. Proficiency in English writing includes the ability to write effectively at both the local level—covering vocabulary, grammar, and sentence structure—and the global level, which involves skills such as text organisation, logical reasoning, and argumentation (Lv, 2018, as cited in Wang et al., 2022). The global level highlights the importance of promoting CT skills among EFL learners to achieve writing mastery.

However, with the spread of AI-assisted writing tools in EFL instruction, a critical

question arises: how do students' CT skills fit within this emerging context? Indeed, few studies have focused specifically on exploring CT skills promotion in writing through AI-powered tools. Liu et al. study (2021) investigated the effectiveness of a new approach called Reflective Thinking Promotion-based AI-supported English Writing (RTP-AIEW), which promotes learners' reflective thinking to improve writing quality. They conducted comparative quasi-experimental research involving two university EFL writing classes. the RTP-AIEW approach and a conventional AI-supported approach. As a result, findings revealed that the RTP-AIEW approach effectively incorporates AI-supported writing feedback into EFL instruction since it led to improvements in students' writing abilities, self-efficacy, self-regulated learning, and reduced cognitive load.

Likewise, in another study, researchers integrated peer assessment (PA) based on knowledge-building theory with AWE in an EFL writing class. Results showed that this approach improved students' EFL writing performance, motivation, and CT while reducing EFL writing anxiety (C.-C. Liu et al., 2023). Indeed, cognitive overload and anxiety are barriers that can indirectly interfere with a learner's CT skills. Gayed et al.'s study (2022) explored the impact of an AI-based writing assistant tool called "AI KAKU" on reducing cognitive barriers learners encounter while producing English text. They found that AI KAKU had a significant positive effect on reducing cognitive barriers after

experimentation with two groups of Japanese students.

Lastly, another study (Guo et al., 2022) suggested using a chatbot-assisted approach to enhance one aspect of CT skills in writing which is argumentative writing. For this reason, the authors developed a chatbot system called "Argumate" to scaffold students' argument construction and evaluated its positive impact on helping students produce high-quality argumentative writing.

Despite the limited research on using AI-powered tools to develop EFL learners' CT skills in writing, the current body of knowledge does not primarily focus on this issue. Furthermore, machines tend to prioritize surface errors over contextual issues, and participants' familiarity with typing in English which presents additional constraints (Gayed et al., 2022). Nonetheless, the chatbot-assisted approach used in Guo et al.'s study (2022) appears to be promising. However, it has limitations, including difficulty handling certain types of input and limited capacity to address higher-order concerns as they reported.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employs a mixed-method approach to investigate perceptions about the development of students' CT through the use of AI-powered tools in an EFL context. The quantitative component rigorously analyses the data to uncover underlying patterns and relationships, whereas the qualitative component

provides an in-depth exploration of subjective experiences.

3.2 Participants and Data Collection

The participants in this study comprised 30 EFL master students at the University of Djelfa, Algeria, completed a questionnaire, while six EFL teachers participated in interviews. The questionnaire comprised 14 closed-ended questions, designed to gauge students' perceptions and experiences with AI-powered tools in their writing process. To select participants, a purposeful sampling was used, focusing on second-year Master's students as they are considered more experienced and have undergone various stages of development in their EFL writing skills. Furthermore, for the interviews, a convenience sampling method was employed, considering time constraints and limited teacher availability. The structured interviews, lasting approximately 20 minutes each, incorporated both closed-ended and open-ended questions to explore teachers' views on the impact of AI tools on students' CT development in EFL writing.

3.3 Data Analysis

The responses from the questionnaires were analysed using SPSS statistical software to identify trends and patterns in students' perceptions through both descriptive and inferential statistics. The results are presented in the form of tables and graphs for better clarity. On the other hand, To analyse the teachers' interviews, a thematic analysis was conducted to identify key themes and insights related to the use of AI-powered tools for CT development in EFL writing.

4. Results

The current study aimed to investigate both teachers' and students' perceptions regarding the use of AI-powered tools in EFL writing and their impact on the development of students' CT skills. Moreover, it explored the challenges that EFL students face while using these tools in their writing process. To gather data, questionnaires were administered to 30 second-year EFL master students and interviews were conducted with six EFL teachers. Analysis of this data revealed the following main results.

4.1 Quantitative Analysis of Students' Questionnaires

Most students reported occasionally using AI-powered tools to assist with their

Fig.1. Frequency of AI-powered Tool Use in Writing

writing tasks. Specifically, 66.7% use AI tools for writing 'sometimes,' while 33.3% use them 'every time,' as shown in Figure 1.

Fig.2. Use of AI Tools as Support in Writing

We asked respondents whether AI-powered tools provide adequate support in areas where they struggle with writing. The majority, representing 86.7% of the sample, selected 'Yes', while the remaining 13.3% chose 'No', as illustrated in Figure 2.

positive,' while 26.67% described it as 'Very positive.' Figure 4 presents the frequency distribution of the results.

The median value, as shown in Table 1, is 4, indicating a central tendency toward a 'somewhat positive' impact of AI-powered

Figure 3 displays the frequency distribution of the results obtained after asking respondents about their agreement on whether using AI-powered tools helps them learn and improve their writing skills independently.

tools on students' CT in writing. Additionally, the skewness value is

Most students reported that using AI-powered tools has a positive impact, to varying degrees, on the development of their CT skills in writing. Specifically, 36.67% of the students perceive the impact as 'Somewhat

negative (-0.843), suggesting that most students' opinions are clustered toward the right side of the graph, representing 'Somewhat positive' and 'Very positive' responses.

Table 1. Central Tendency Statistics

Statistics		
Impact on critical thinking		
N	Valid	30
	Missing	0
Median		4.00
Skewness		-.843
Std. Error of Skewness		.427

Most respondents who answered 'No' to whether AI-powered tools provide adequate support in areas where they struggle in writing showed a negative impression regarding the impact on their CT in writing, as illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2. Impact on CT vs AI Support Association

		Impact on critical thinking				
		Very negative	Somewhat negative	Neutral	Somewhat positive	Very positive
Provide adequate support	No	33.3%	50.0%	0.0%	18.2%	0.0%
	Yes	66.7%	50.0%	100.0%	81.8%	100.0%

To expand on the previous question and gain deeper insights, we asked students which aspect of CT in EFL writing they found most enhanced by using AI-powered tools. The majority of respondents (60%) identified 'Creating' as the most positively impacted aspect, followed by 'Understanding' and 'Analysing,' each at 40%, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Percentage Distribution of CT Aspects

Aspects of critical thinking	Percent of Cases
Remembering	26.7%
Understanding	40.0%
Applying	26.7%
Analysing	40.0%
Evaluating	30.0%
Creating	60.0%

Students encounter certain challenges while using AI tools in writing. Indeed, over-reliance on AI emerged as the most significant challenge faced by respondents when using AI-powered tools for their writing tasks, as reported by 53.3% of them. The second most significant challenge, highlighted by 46.7% of respondents, is the lack of personalisation in AI-powered tools, particularly in providing feedback or assistance tailored to

students' specific needs or learning styles. Table 4 presents the percentage distribution of these challenges.

Table 4. Percentage Distribution of Challenges

Challenges	Percent of Cases
Feedback clarity	30.0%
Technical issues	30.0%
Lack of personalisation	46.7%
Overreliance concerns	53.3%

To explore potential reasons why students may have negative impressions regarding the impact of AI tools on their CT in writing, we examined patterns in the crosstabulation between students' impressions and challenges, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Impact on CT vs Challenges Association

		Challenges			
		Feedback clarity	Technical issues	Lack of personalisation	Overreliance concerns
Impact on critical thinking	Very negative	0.0%	0.0%	66.7%	100.0%
	Somewhat negative	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	50.0%
	Neutral	50.0%	50.0%	33.3%	33.3%
	Somewhat positive	45.5%	27.3%	36.4%	63.6%
	Very positive	12.5%	37.5%	50.0%	37.5%

Percentages and totals are based on respondents.

Consequently, we observed that negative impressions are concentrated around the challenges of 'Lack of personalization' and 'Overreliance concerns.'

4.2 Qualitative Analysis of Teachers' Interviews

After conducting a thematic analysis of teachers' interviews, we identified the following themes:

Theme 01: The Role of AI Tools in Enhancing Students' CT in Writing

Teachers noted that AI tools have the potential to improve students' CT in writing in several ways. Firstly, they may contribute to the development of students' linguistic competence, as AI-powered tools can provide immediate feedback on their

writing, particularly regarding vocabulary and grammar, as reported by the following teachers:

- Teacher 1: *"AI can provide instant, tailored feedback on writing, helping students identify and correct mistakes in grammar, vocabulary, and structure."*

- Teacher 2: *"... in addition to new vocabulary. They guide them to produce correct grammatical structures regarding verb tenses and conjunctions... This can be acquired by checking the correctness of their writing or asking AI tools to spot and correct mistakes."*
- Teacher 3: *"AI tools can provide instant, detailed feedback on grammar, style, and coherence. This helps students identify weaknesses and improve their writing."*

Secondly, teachers acknowledged that AI tools could stimulate students' creativity in writing. Indeed, AI-powered tools help students generate content and explore new

insights, which might enhance their creativity, as noted by many teachers:

- Teacher 1: *"...when used appropriately to generate ideas or explore research paths, these tools can actually expand their creativity and foster deeper critical thinking."*
- Teacher 2: *"Yes, they help them gain new insights to include in their writing."*
- Teacher 3: *"AI-powered language models can offer alternative phrasing and perspectives, allowing students to explore different ways of expressing ideas. This encourages them to critically evaluate various stylistic and rhetorical choices."*

Finally, several teachers reported that AI tools can be used to scaffold learning in writing, as they offer ways to challenge students, promote autonomous learning, and enhance engagement and motivation:

- Teacher 1: *"AI can generate a variety of writing prompts and exercises tailored to different skill levels. This encourages students to think creatively and critically as they respond to diverse topics and challenges."*
- Teacher 2: *"By analyzing AI's feedback, students learn to critically assess their own work and understand areas for improvement."*

- Teacher 3: *"They offer significant advantages, such as sometimes acting as a virtual editor or supervisor."*
- Teacher 4: *"Interactive AI tools can make learning more engaging and interactive, potentially increasing students' motivation and interest in their studies."*
- Teacher 5: *"One additional aspect to consider is the role of AI in fostering deeper engagement with the writing process."*

Theme 02: Concerns about Overreliance on AI Tools in Writing

Despite teachers' positive attitudes towards the use of AI tools for promoting students' CT in writing, many expressed concerns about their use. Specifically, they reported that overreliance on these tools has the potential to hinder learning, limit creativity, and lead to cheating and laziness:

- Teacher 1: *"... However, overreliance on these tools can hinder learning."*
- Teacher 2: *"... However, it may be detrimental to learners' progress if they use AI tools to cheat or to do their homework without making any attempt."*

- Teacher 3: “... *They can also lead to laziness and a lack of independent thinking.*”
- Teacher 4: “... *Students might become overly dependent on AI tools, potentially undermining their ability to develop critical thinking and self-editing skills.*”
- Teacher 5: “... *If students rely too much on AI for ready-made ideas, it can kill their creativity.*”

5. Discussion

This section discusses the implications of the present study's findings, which reveal several important insights regarding the impact of using AI-powered tools in developing students' CT in EFL writing, with the existing literature and explores how they address the study's research questions.

Using AI tools in writing has the potential to aid students in developing their writing at both local and global levels according to the current study's results. Indeed, students reported improvements in their linguistic competence, including vocabulary and grammar, through real-time correction and feedback features provided by AI-powered tools. These findings align with Rugaiyah's study, which highlights the powerful role of instant feedback in enhancing learners' linguistic competence by allowing them to identify and correct mistakes immediately,

leading to faster and more effective learning (Rugaiyah, 2023). On the other hand, the present study also examined the impact of AI use at a global level, particularly in relation to CT skills development in writing. Therefore, findings suggest that AI tools can enhance students' creativity by assisting them in synthesising information from various sources, generating and exploring new insights, and applying knowledge and skills to produce original, coherent, and well-structured texts. Correspondingly, a study conducted during the 2023-2024 academic year investigated the effects of ParagraphAI, an AI writing tool, on the CT skills of ten third-semester students in the English Tadris Study Program at IAIN Curup. The researchers obtained similar results, demonstrating that ParagraphAI can aid students in argument structuring, producing coherent writing, and exploring new knowledge areas (Nabilla et al., 2024). Furthermore, this study's results indicate that AI-powered tools can provide adequate support in writing, as reported by both students and teachers. In fact, these tools can foster autonomous learning, engagement, and motivation, as well as reducing students' cognitive load which can positively impact their CT skills improvement in writing. This conclusion aligns with the findings of Song & Song's (2023) experiment, which underscore the efficacy of ChatGPT, an AI tool, in enhancing students' motivation in writing,

as reflected in improvements in organisational skills, coherence, grammar, and vocabulary.

Despite the previously mentioned positive effects of AI tools on learners' CT in writing, participants in our study also acknowledged certain challenges. Findings revealed that overreliance was viewed as the most significant concern. Likewise, teachers elaborated on this issue, warning that dependence on AI could impede students' development of essential self-editing, independent thinking, and creative skills. The latter aligns with Zhai et al. (2024) systematic review, which examined the effects of overreliance on AI dialogue systems on students' cognitive abilities. The findings of their research indicated that while incorporating AI dialogue systems in academic writing courses in college and higher education offers benefits, it can also introduce challenges such as overreliance, diminished creativity, and ethical issues like plagiarism and biased data. In addition, students, in our study, have reported that the lack of personalisation of AI-powered tools presents sometimes a hurdle to their progress in writing since the provided feedback or assistance does not always address their specific needs or learning style. This matches with the findings in Nerem et al. (2024) study, which highlighted teacher participants' concerns about the accuracy and reliability of AI-generated texts to provide personalised education.

The findings of the current investigation suggest that AI tools have substantial potential to enhance CT skills in EFL writing by supporting creativity, linguistic competence, and autonomous learning. However, the challenges identified, especially regarding overreliance and lack of personalisation, indicate the need for a balanced and mindful integration of AI in language instruction. As a matter of fact, teachers may play a pivotal role in guiding students toward using AI tools in ways that promote their independent thinking and creative skills; simultaneously, AI developers could focus on enhancing personalisation features to provide targeted feedback that aligns with students' learning needs and learning styles. Even though this study provides valuable insights, several limitations should be noted. The sample size was relatively small, and the study focused on master's-level students, which may limit generalisability. Therefore, further research is recommended to explore strategies for integrating AI tools that limit overreliance and encourage critical engagement with content across different educational contexts.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study contributes to our understanding of the role of AI-powered tools in developing CT skills in EFL writing. Although the potential benefits are significant, especially in areas of creativity and autonomous learning, challenges such

as overreliance and lack of personalisation remain critical considerations. Educators and developers must work together to ensure AI tools enhance, rather than hinder, the teaching and learning experience.

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